

A Note on Solid Sugars from Mohuwa Flower Syrup.

BY D. G. WALAWALKAR.

Mohuwa (*Bassia Latifolia*) flower is claimed to contain a large percentage of sugars, especially sucrose. Church (*Nature*, 1886, 33, 343) reported only 3.2% of cane sugar from air-dried flowers; Elsworthy (*J. Soc. Chem. Ind.*, 1887, 21) reported that the cane sugar content varies from 4.6-17.1% according to the locality from which the flowers are gathered. But Fowler and co-workers (*J. Ind. Inst. Sci.*, 1920, 3, 81) report as much as 28.8% of sucrose. In order to exploit the commercial possibility of obtaining sucrose, if available, in such large quantities and in general to prepare solid sugars like jaggery from the Mohuwa syrup, the following experiments were conducted.

EXPERIMENTAL.

The analytical figures for sucrose and non-reducing sugars agreed with those of Fowler (*loc. cit.*). Attempts were made to prepare solids like jaggery by atomisation of the syrup on a hot plate and making composite briquettes with cane sugar and the syrup.

10 Lbs. of the flowers were treated with water (6 litres) and repeatedly leached out when a solution of 29 Brix was obtained. It was concentrated in vacuum to different strengths ranging from 54 to 84 Brix. The syrup was darker in colour.

300 C.c. of 32 Brix syrup was shaken with 6 g. of 'Suchar' and boiled for 1 hour under stirring and then filtered. No appreciable decolourisation was obtained. Similar treatment with 'Bone char' effected an appreciable removal of colour and a lighter syrup was obtained. Sulphur dioxide and chlorine after liming (to p_H 8) failed to decolourise. All attempts to crystallise even with seeding of pure sucrose and laevulose failed to start crystallisation.

Next the syrup was atomised by means of a small hand sprayer on a dry steam-heated aluminium sheet, 1/16" thick. The spray dried immediately and could be scraped off into a powder. However, it rapidly absorbed moisture from air and after a while became syrupy.

Attempts were made to make briquettes of sugar by using the Mohuwa syrup as a binding material to obtain a product similar to jaggery. Experiments were conducted with various proportions of sugar and syrup. Solid was obtained with 84% Brix syrup and sugar if they were in the ratio of 1: 2. A few representative data are given below:

Sugar.	Syrup.	Remarks.
240 g.	120 g.	Soft to touch
350	100	Hard and well-set jaggery
500	100	Solid, very hard cake

All syrups, prepared, showed *laevo*-rotation thus showing a preponderance of reducing sugars.

In view of the above experiments it is suggested that it is impossible to crystallise sucrose from Mohuwa flower syrup. Further it has to be noted that all workers so far have not directly obtained and estimated sucrose from the syrup. Riche and Remouart (*J. Pharm. Chem.*, 1880, 215) mention that air-dried flowers contain 60% sugars of which $\frac{1}{4}$ th is crystallisable. Even this is only an estimate and they have not obtained the crystallised product. It is not probable, therefore, that what is usually taken as sucrose by indirect estimation may be higher saccharides and not sucrose.

SUGAR TECHNOLOGY LABORATORY,
J. V. D. COLLEGE OF SCIENCE AND TECHNOLOGY,
WALTAIR.

Received August 17, 1956.